

THE ROLE OF THE INTERNET IN THE SPREAD OF FAKE INFORMATION

Ziyodullayeva Khumora

Student of international journalism faculty
of Uzbekistan State University of world languages.

Bo'ronov Nazim

Scientific leader:

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Annotation. In this thesis, about the role of the internet in the dissemination of fake information, which is currently developing with relevance, to what extent it has become popular among young people, as well as how social network users look at them. In particular, within the framework of this topical topic, the research of several researchers was studied and analyzed them from a psychological point of view.

Keywords: phishing, advertising, information security, data, technology, fake, ideas, public.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the internet plays a crucial role in human life. The influence of traditional news sources like newspapers and television is declining, becoming less significant in the reception of news. Specifically, the expansion of social media infrastructures like **Facebook**, **Instagram**, and **Twitter** plays a vital role in disrupting traditional mass media. People use these social networks to connect with friends and relatives and gather information and news from around the world. Compared to traditional media, receiving news through social networks is much faster and cheaper. Additionally, it is much easier to share news with your friends and others for discussions. It must be acknowledged that today, a large number of **"fake news"** victims are young people. This is because young users tend to use social networks more frequently than middle-aged or older users. **"Fake news"** appears on social media in the form of videos, audio, photos, and texts.

Most school students, whether they understand it or not, tend to believe in these things. Among the companies fighting against **"fake news"** are **Facebook**, **YouTube**, and **Google**. For instance, **Facebook** launched a campaign that uses Facebook notifications and newspaper ads to advise consumers on how to detect **fake news** [1]. Moreover, the **"Perspective"** project has been collaborating with **"The New York Times"** magazine for ten years [2] In July 2018, **YouTube** announced measures to stop the distribution of fake news

videos.[3] It is also worth mentioning the “*Perspective*” project developed by Jigsaw, a subsidiary of *Google*. The goal of this project is to improve the area of website commentary through machine learning capabilities.

R. Chesney, D. Citron [4], and M. Westerlund [5] were the first researchers to note and develop the thesis that the term “*fake*” may not fully describe a new type of misinformation. The purpose of the research is to describe and predict the impact of fake technology on global and national political dialogue. The methodology also includes systematizing theoretical information, classifying, analyzing, and predicting a set of factors. Additionally, one of the most effective tools for influencing and manipulating the public is fake news in the form of photo and video. Despite these negative factors, fake news is becoming increasingly popular. This is because readers cannot immediately recognize falsified information and either fully or partially believe in the described facts.

CONCLUSION

Modern mass media influences all areas of human life, including cultural and educational processes. The growing flow of information requires an individual not only to adequately perceive and effectively process the information but also to creatively understand and critically analyze media messages. From this perspective, the goal of media education as an integral part of modern education is to develop an individual’s media competence.

In conclusion, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of developing a set of measures aimed at preventing the spread of fake news and mitigating the consequences of such distribution. The journalistic community needs to demand a sufficient approach not only when broadcasting news from social networks but also requires an audience of intelligent readers who have at least mastered the basics of media literacy. The “*Fake news*” epidemic sets the task of restoring trust in mass media among audiences who increasingly prefer to receive information through social networks.

List of literature used:

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